

Scaling New Horizons in Higher Education: Empowering Educators and Reimagining the Student Experience in Large Classes

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Abstract

This paper explores the significance of large class teaching in the context of escalating university enrolments and the growing diversity of student populations. It emphasizes the pressing need to transform large classes into active and collaborative learning environments and away from didactic delivery of information. While educational technology plays a role in this transformation, it should be noted that it is not the sole solution. The paper highlights the challenges faced by educators in maintaining quality teaching in large classes and proposes networked teaching as a viable approach to address these challenges. It also explores the personal and professional benefits of large class teaching, along with strategies for constant improvement. The Connected Learning at Scale (CLaS) project is introduced as a comprehensive case study, discussing its co-design challenges, impact demonstration, and the importance of sharing best practices. It concludes by urging educators to involve additional stakeholders in the design process to enhance the student experience and foster deeper learning.

Keywords: *Higher education; large classes; networked teaching; student engagement; co-design*

1. Introduction

The current landscape of higher education is characterized by a consistent rise in university enrolments and an increasingly diverse student body. As a consequence, large class teaching has become a prominent concern (Gannaway et al., 2017; Kagan & Diamond, 2019; Ryan et al., 2021; UNESCO, 2017). Large classes are an enduring reality and need to be delivered in vibrant, active and collaborative learning spaces. While experiential learning has been recognized as a powerful pedagogical approach (Black et al., 2021; Kolb & Kolb, 2009; Lynch & Pappas, 2017; Miller & Maellaro, 2016), its implementation at scale remains a complex challenge (Mantai & Huber, 2021). Amongst these is the challenge of managing a team of tutors or teaching assistants and ensuring consistency across these multiple teams for the student experience and indeed maintaining student engagement (Clancy et al., 2021). Moreover, while educational technology can support large class teaching (Bryant, 2018; Yang et al., 2018), it should be acknowledged that it is not the panacea for all the issues faced (Kane, 2019; Ryan et al., 2021).

This paper explores the importance of adopting networked teaching practices which involve viewing teaching as a networked activity rather than relying solely on the direct relationship between educators and students (Mantai & Huber, 2021). By embracing networked teaching, educators can effectively coordinate and manage the various elements within the teaching and learning process, such as learning management systems, learning technologies, tutors, fellow teachers, students as teachers and peer reviewers, learning designers, and educational developers. Understanding the networked nature of teaching can alleviate the burden on educators and unlock new possibilities for enhancing the student experience.

2. Networked Teaching

Traditionally, teaching has been a siloed activity with the educator having complete control and responsibility for the learning, teaching and assessment activities, including the design, delivery, marking and improvements. The quality of teaching and resulting learning experiences has been associated with the direct relationship between educators and students (Broadbent, 2018; Gannaway et al., 2017). However, as class sizes grow, this perspective often leads to faculty anxiety and a sense of loss of control (Hubbard & Tallents, 2020). Educators can struggle to maintain the illusion of control, resulting in frustration and burnout (Mantai & Huber, 2021). It is crucial therefore to recognize that teaching is a networked activity, where the educator acts as a coordinator and manager of various elements within the teaching and learning process. This includes learning management systems, learning technologies, tutors, fellow teachers, students as teachers and reviewers, learning designers, and educational developers.

Indeed, there are a range of roles involved in a networked teaching approach, each with its own responsibilities. As well as a large teaching team that may consist of lecturers and teaching assistants/tutors, the educator may be joined by others in the design process - educational developers, learning designers and educational technologists. Input through pedagogical advice, latest research on teaching methods, new tools and platforms to achieve learning outcomes and professional development support as well as liaison with ICT units. Then there may be industry partners who can bring in authentic contexts and perspectives to the classroom, library personnel who can support academic literacy skills, media officers and producers who can advise and support the creation of interactive and quality learning media objects, research assistants who can support the development of an evaluation plan to see how any new interventions are playing out in practice and finally the students. They can be instrumental in peer reviews, peer assisted learning support, developing resources and co-designing. Understanding this networked nature of teaching can alleviate the burden on educators and open up new possibilities for enhancing the student experience. That said, this is a transformational move away from a siloed approach and not one many experienced educators may be comfortable with.

3. Benefits of Large Class Teaching

Although perceived barriers to facilitating large classes can dominate, large class teaching can offer both personal and professional benefits for educators. By engaging in transformative teaching practices, educators can experience continuous growth and development, leading to personal satisfaction and a sense of professional achievement (Mantai & Huber, 2021). Participants in their study cited benefits including the ability to harness a greater energy in a large classroom, better participation, diversity of thought and ideas, as well as benefits to society through increased student access to, and development of, knowledge, leading to greater meaning to their roles as educators. Additionally, large class teaching provides a unique opportunity to transform the student experience as they too benefit from the diversity and participation opportunities (Bryant, 2022b). Recognizing the benefits associated with large class teaching, it is important to support educators in their journey of innovation and improvement. Whilst funding is helpful in terms of 'buying time', more often than not it is usually not available, so we also recommend looking for alternative ways of working with colleagues and other interested stakeholders in the design and development journey.

4. Co-Design approaches

In education, co-design is a facilitated, team-based approach which brings actors together to design a solution to an overarching educational need or problem (Roschelle et al., 2006).

Co-design in a broader context involves active and collaborative participation from a diverse set of stakeholders (Manzini, 2015). It can also be defined as “a practice where people collaborate or connect their knowledge, skills, and resources in order to carry out a design task” (Zamenopoulos & Alexiou, 2018, p. 10). What Co-design is not, and is often confused as, is student surveys and feedback, inviting guest speakers or industry experts to present, or peer observation of teaching. All of these are valid activities that contribute to quality learning and teaching, but they are not co-design. Co-design as a term has risen in prominence lately and is often found masquerading under other ‘titles’ such as lived-experience, participatory approaches, students as partners, and user-experience design. But what is consistent across any definition is the underpinning philosophy that learners are included as collaborators or partners in the process of designing their learning journey.

5. Connected Learning at Scale (CLaS)

The Connected Learning at Scale (CLaS) project serves as a valuable case study in the context of large class teaching. The project was initiated to transform the student experience in specific units with high student enrolments (Bryant, 2022a). The aim was to co-design interventions using a range of strategies we label as deep, medium, and light approaches (Wilson et al., 2021; Zeivots et al., 2023). Each approach involves to some extent or another implementing innovations across three simple principles:

- (1) Information engagement – where students both individually and collectively engage with discipline knowledge as opposed to having it broadcast at them in a lecture.
- (2) Connected participation and active learning - where face-to-face teaching time, student learning activities and technology are leveraged to build connections and networks to address, debate and solve critical global and local challenges through innovative pedagogical approaches.
- (3) Relevant and authentic assessment and feed-forward – where learning is applied and tested through authentic assessment modes supported by opportunities to receive and share feedback from both academics and their peers.

As would be expected in a project of this size and complexity, we encountered numerous challenges ranging from gaining buy-in from faculty, to navigating differing teaching styles; not to mention the need to ‘change’ whilst in the middle of another large scale change - the rapid move to remote teaching due to the COVID-19 pandemic. This highlights the need in these larger projects to allow enough time for building trust and capacity through and in the co-design process. The CLaS project also emphasizes the importance of thinking differently about the ways educators work and cultivating a mindset that is receptive to innovative approaches and collaborative endeavours. Integrating opportunities for academic professional development into the project through the co-design

process, can ensure another outcome of the project, capacity building in learning design and sustainable futures (Voogt et al., 2015).

6. Sharing Practice and Demonstrating Impact

To create a meaningful and lasting impact, it is essential to share best practices and showcase successful interventions. Gribble and Beckman (2022) espouse a 4Cs approach to disseminating innovations in a university setting: classroom, corridors, campus and community. In the CLaS project this has been achieved through various means, such as organizing showcase sessions both within the Business School and the University of Sydney as well as at local and international conferences, where educators can present their innovative teaching methods and strategies. Additionally, building a website or blog, dedicated to sharing experiences, insights, and resources can serve as a valuable platform for disseminating knowledge (<http://cdrg.blog>). Embracing the concept of patterns that can be reproduced in different contexts further contributes to the scalability and sustainability of innovative teaching practices (see <https://clasdesignpatterns.com>).

Celebrating participation and recognizing the contributions of stakeholders play a pivotal role in creating a culture of continuous improvement. Moreover, it is crucial to move beyond the initial engagement and consulting stages, where educators are "doing for" stakeholders, and transition towards a more balanced and collaborative approach of "doing with" stakeholders (Dollinger et al., 2022). By involving stakeholders throughout the design and implementation process, their expertise and perspectives are valued, leading to more inclusive and effective educational practices (Vallis et al., 2022).

7. Conclusion

In conclusion, the paper underscores the importance of addressing the challenges posed by large class teaching in higher education. It advocates for networked teaching practices, which acknowledge the complex and interconnected nature of teaching, and emphasizes the personal and professional benefits that educators can derive from large class teaching. The paper highlights the Connected Learning at Scale (CLaS) project as a case study, showcasing the significance of co-design, sharing best practices, and demonstrating impact. Moreover, it urges educators to involve additional stakeholders in the design process to create a more authentic and enriching learning experience for students. While involving others in the design process may require additional time and effort, the rewards in terms of improved student experience and deeper learning outcomes justify the investment. By embracing innovation, collaboration, and the networked nature of teaching, educators can

empower themselves and reimagine the student experience in large classes, paving the way for a transformative and inclusive higher education landscape.

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